

MAXIMAL CONTINUANTS AND PERIODICITY

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Abstract

A regular or singular continuant is the denominator of a terminating regular or singular continued fraction, interpreted as a function of the partial denominators. A continuant is called maximal, resp. minimal, if any permutation of the entries, except for their reversion, gives a smaller, resp. greater, value. The determination of the structures of the maximal and minimal regular and of the minimal singular continuants turned out to be a purely combinatorial word problem. The structure of the maximal singular continuants is known only if the entries are pairwise different or if they are taken from any set of two integers greater than 1. The author has shown that in both cases the problem is again purely combinatorial, and that the palindromic (i.e., symmetric) continuants are in a one-to-one correspondence with the Fine-Wilf words with two coprime periods. In the present paper we settle the analogous question for non-palindromic maximal continuants. We characterize them by a periodicity property and obtain an explicit description of the places of the letters by Beatty sequences. The proof makes use of an algorithmic construction of a class of balanced words which iterates two formal substitutions and can be described in terms of a certain semiregular continued fraction expansion. We also give a short alternate proof of the characterization of palindromic maximal continuants.

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–Dedicated to Prof. P. M. Gruber on the occasion of his 65th birthday

1. Introduction

Given a real x , we consider the representation $x = a_0 + \frac{1}{a_1 + \frac{1}{a_2 + \dots + \frac{1}{a_n}}}$ by a regular continued fraction with entries $a_0 \in \mathbf{Z}$, $a_1, a_2, \dots \in \mathbf{N}$, and also the representation $x = a_0 - \frac{1}{a_1 - \frac{1}{a_2 - \dots - \frac{1}{a_n}}}$ with entries $a_0 \in \mathbf{Z}$, $a_1, a_2, \dots \in \mathbf{N} \setminus \{1\}$. The terminating fractions $a_0 + \frac{1}{a_1 + \frac{1}{a_2 + \dots + \frac{1}{a_n}}}$ and $a_0 - \frac{1}{a_1 - \frac{1}{a_2 - \dots - \frac{1}{a_n}}}$ ($n = 1, 2, \dots$) reduce to rationals $\frac{p_n}{q_n}$ and $\frac{P_n}{Q_n}$ in lowest terms. Since the denominators q_n and Q_n are independent of a_0 , we will write $q_n = q(a_1, \dots, a_n)$ and $Q_n = Q(a_1, \dots, a_n)$. Interpreted as functions of the variables a_1, \dots, a_n , the denominators are known as (regular, resp. singular) *continuants*. A basic property of continuants is their invariance under reversion, hence we will occasionally identify a sequence $Q = (a_1, \dots, a_n)$ with its reversal $Q^* = (a_n, \dots, a_1)$ without making explicit mention.

The following problem has attracted some attention: Given a sequence of integers $A = (\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n) = (c_1, \dots, c_1; c_2, \dots, c_2; \dots; c_r, \dots, c_r) = (c_1^{\ell_1}; c_2^{\ell_2}; \dots; c_r^{\ell_r})$, $1 \leq c_1 < \dots < c_r$ ($2 \leq c_i$ in the singular case), with multiplicities $\ell_i \in \mathbf{N}$, $\sum \ell_i = n$ (throughout the paper exponents will be used to denote repetitions of a letter or subword), find the permutation (i_1, \dots, i_n) which makes $Q(\alpha_{i_1}, \dots, \alpha_{i_n})$, resp. $q(\alpha_{i_1}, \dots, \alpha_{i_n})$ extremal. A continuant is called *maximal (minimal)* if the arrangement of its entries is maximizing (minimizing).

T.W.Cusick [3] found the maximizing arrangements for regular continuants in the case $A = (1^\ell; 2^{n-\ell})$. T.S.Motzkin and E.G.Straus [6] constructed the extremal regular continuants in the case of pairwise different entries $1 \leq \alpha_1 < \alpha_2 < \dots < \alpha_n$. In [7] the author tackled the general case, an arbitrary sequence A being admitted. He determined the extremal arrangements for regular and the minimizing arrangements for singular continuants by a purely combinatorial argument. These results have led to various applications in the metrical theory of continued fractions [8], transcendence theory (C.Baxa [2]) and complexity theory (see J.Shallit & J.Sorensen [11], and recent work by the author [10]).

The problem involving maximal singular continuants turned out to be of a totally different nature and is still far from being completely solved. There are interesting and unexpected connections with combinatorial word problems. The partial answers available and extensive experimental evidence indicate that the structure of this type of continuants is highly unstable with respect to changes of A , in remarkable contrast to the behaviour of the three other types.

In [9] the author studied the case of sequences $A = (\alpha_1, \dots, \alpha_n) = (a^\ell; b^m)$ ($\ell + m = n$, $\ell \geq 2$, $m \geq 0$), of arbitrary length $n \geq 2$, made up of two different integers ($2 \leq a < b$). He proved that the problem is again purely combinatorial, that is, the permutation giving the maximal continuant $Q_{\ell,m}$ made up of ℓ a 's and m b 's does not depend on the choice of a, b , which makes its determination a combinatorial word problem. He established an algorithmic

procedure which allows to construct each $Q_{\ell,m}$ in at most $2 \log(\ell+m)$ steps by iterating two formal substitutions. This procedure is intimately related with a Euclidean type algorithm which induces a semiregular continued fraction expansion via the shift $\tau : (0, \infty) \setminus \mathbf{N} \rightarrow (0, \infty)$, given by

$$\tau x = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{x} - \lfloor \frac{1}{x} \rfloor} - 1 \quad (x \in (0, 1)), \quad \tau x = \frac{1}{\lceil x \rceil - x} - 1 \quad (x \in (1, \infty) \setminus \mathbf{N}),$$

which is a mixture of the regular Gauss shift $\frac{1}{x} - \lfloor \frac{1}{x} \rfloor$ ($x \in (0, 1)$) and the singular (backward) shift $\lceil \frac{1}{y} \rceil - \frac{1}{y}$ ($y \in (0, 1)$).

The words $Q = Q_{\ell,m}$ can be uniquely described by certain terminating semiregular expansions (see [9] and [10]). The continuants Q were found to be palindromic (i.e., symmetric) precisely if $\ell-1, m+1$ are coprime, and the palindromic continuants are precisely the words $Q = (aFa)$, where F runs through the Fine-Wilf words with two coprime periods. Since the places of the letters in a Fine-Wilf word are given explicitly by Beatty sequences, this description carries over to the palindromic continuants. For further contributions related to these questions and for additional references the reader may consult the original paper of Fine and Wilf [4] and more recent work by R.Tijdeman, R.J.Simpson and L.Zamboni [13], [14], [15], J.Berstel and L.Boasson [1] and Zhi-Wei Sun [12].

In this paper we complete the investigations done in [9]. We present the characterization of non-palindromic maximal continuants $Q_{\ell,m}$ ($\gcd(\ell-1, m+1) \geq 2$) by periodicity properties and describe them explicitly in terms of Beatty sequences. The idea of the proof is to combine the following two bijections: first, there is a one-to-one correspondence between non-palindromic continuants and a class of palindromic continuants which are uniquely determined by certain semiregular expansions; second, the Fine-Wilf words F , and so the palindromic continuants as their extensions $Q = (aFa)$, can be described by regular continued fractions. We need a translation between the two expansions which is developed in section 2. As our arguments rely on the properties of palindromic continuants, we found it worthwhile to enclose a short alternate and more natural proof of the representation $Q = (aFa)$ which is based on the algorithmic construction of Q and the characterization of the Fine-Wilf words F as being bi-balanced.

We mention that the connection between maximality and periodicity gets weaker in dimension three and breaks down in higher dimensions. In the case $r=3$, that is, for sequences $A = (c_1^{\ell_1}; c_2^{\ell_2}; c_3^{\ell_3})$ with three digits ($2 \leq c_1 < c_2 < c_3$), one can still specify a (rather large) subset of integer triples (ℓ_1, ℓ_2, ℓ_3) for which there is a purely combinatorial analogue to the two-dimensional theorem, but nothing of this kind seems to be true for $r \geq 4$. This is one of the aspects of the exceptional behaviour of the Tijdeman-Simpson algorithm [13] for the construction of the Fine-Wilf words in dimension two. Kraaikamp and Meester [5] observed that the metrical properties of the underlying dynamical process are also different in the two-dimensional case.

2. Preliminaries and Statement of Results

We recall some definitions (see e.g. [14]). A word made up of two letters a, b is called *balanced* if in any two subwords of equal length the number of occurrences of any of the letters differs by at most 1. We call a word W *left-balanced*, resp. *right-balanced*, if it is balanced and the extended word (aWb) , resp. (bWa) , is still balanced, and we call it *bi-balanced* if it is both right- and left-balanced. The length of a word W will be denoted by $|W|$.

Theorem 1. *There is a one-to-one correspondence between the non-primitive points in \mathbf{N}^2 and the non-palindromic maximal continuants made up of two letters a, b ($a < b$). Given any triple of positive integers $(y, t; d)$ such that y, t are coprime and $d \geq 2$, let Π be the word in which the places of the b 's are given by the numbers $\lfloor \frac{k(y+t)}{t} \rfloor$, $k = 1, \dots, t$. Then one obtains a non-palindromic maximal continuant from the word $(Wb) = (\Pi^d)$ by skipping the b on the right end and adding an a on the left end. Conversely, each non-palindromic maximal continuant or its reversal is arising in this way. The word W is left-balanced but not right-balanced, and the length $\pi = y + t = |\Pi|$ is the shortest period of (Wb) .*

We will derive this from an alternative characterization which shows that each word (Wb) is the second longest or longest purely periodic subword of a Fine-Wilf word and has a second period κ ($\pi < \kappa < \pi d$) in the latter case. We make use of a representation of regular continued fractions by unimodular integer matrices. We introduce the matrices $S = S_{+1} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$, $T = S_{-1} = S^{\text{tr}} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$ and the vector $\mathbf{e} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}$. Let $a_0 \in \mathbf{N}_0$, $a_1, a_2, \dots \in \mathbf{N}$. The following representations for a reduced fraction $\frac{u}{w} \neq \frac{1}{1}$ are well known and easily proved by induction:

$$\frac{u}{w} = [a_0; a_1, \dots, a_{2j+1}] \Leftrightarrow \begin{pmatrix} u \\ w \end{pmatrix} = T^{a_0} S^{a_1} T^{a_2} S^{a_3} \dots T^{a_{2j}} S^{a_{2j+1}-1} \mathbf{e} \quad (a_{2j+1} \geq 2), \quad (1a)$$

$$\frac{u}{w} = [a_0; a_1, \dots, a_{2j}] \Leftrightarrow \begin{pmatrix} u \\ w \end{pmatrix} = T^{a_0} S^{a_1} T^{a_2} S^{a_3} \dots T^{a_{2j-2}} S^{a_{2j-1}} T^{a_{2j}-1} \mathbf{e} \quad (a_{2j} \geq 2) \quad (1b)$$

($j \in \mathbf{N}_0$). In particular, one has $\frac{u}{1} = [u;] \Leftrightarrow \begin{pmatrix} u \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} = T^{u-1} \mathbf{e}$ ($u \geq 2$) and $\frac{1}{w} = [0; w] \Leftrightarrow \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ w \end{pmatrix} = S^{w-1} \mathbf{e}$ ($w \geq 2$). For completeness, we associate $\frac{1}{1} = [1;] = [0; 1]$ with $I\mathbf{e}$ (I the unit matrix). It should be noted that the matrices Y appearing in any of the above representations $\begin{pmatrix} u \\ w \end{pmatrix} = Y\mathbf{e}$ are integer matrices with non-negative entries and determinant 1, and conversely, any matrix from this class has a unique factorization $Y = T^{a_0} S^{a_1} T^{a_2} \dots$ with exponents as in (1).

We now consider an alternative decomposition of these matrices: Starting from the left end of the factorization of $Y = T^{a_0} S^{a_1} T^{a_2} \dots$, there is a unique way of setting brackets to obtain a representation of the form

$$Y = \left(S_{\varepsilon_1}^{v_1} S_{-\varepsilon_1} \right) \left(S_{\varepsilon_2}^{v_2} S_{-\varepsilon_2} \right) \dots \left(S_{\varepsilon_r}^{v_r} S_{-\varepsilon_r} \right) G, \text{ where } G = S^v \text{ or } G = T^v \text{ or } G = I. \quad (2a, b, c)$$

Full information about the factorization (3) is encoded in the sequence $(c_1, \dots, c_r; c)$ with $c_j = \varepsilon_j v_j$ ($j = 1, \dots, r$) and $c = +v, -v, 0$ in the respective cases (2a, b, c). We write

$$\frac{u}{w} = \langle\langle \varepsilon_1 v_1, \dots, \varepsilon_r v_r; c \rangle\rangle \tag{2'}$$

and call this the *semiregular expansion* of $\frac{u}{w}$. We allow the section c_1, \dots, c_r to be empty which happens precisely in the cases $\frac{u}{1} = [u;] = \langle\langle -; -(u-1) \rangle\rangle$ ($u \geq 2$) and $\frac{1}{w} = [0; w] = \langle\langle ; w-1 \rangle\rangle$ ($w \geq 2$). In view of this it makes sense to associate the exceptional fraction $\frac{1}{1} = [1;] = [0; 1]$ with $\langle\langle ; 0 \rangle\rangle$ (in the case $r \geq 1$ one has $v_1 = a_0$, $\varepsilon_1 = -1$ if $a_0 \geq 1$, and $v_1 = a_1$, $\varepsilon_1 = +1$ if $a_0 = 0$). Conversely, given any sequence $(c_1, \dots, c_r; c)$ with $c_j \in \mathbf{Z} \setminus \{0\}$, $r \in \mathbf{N}_0$, $c \in \mathbf{Z}$, it is evident how to recover the regular expansion of the fraction $\frac{u}{w}$ associated with $\binom{u}{w} = Y \binom{1}{1}$. So there is a one-to-one correspondence between the expansions $[a_0; a_1, \dots, a_n] \neq \frac{1}{1}$ and $\langle\langle c_1, \dots, c_r; c \rangle\rangle$.

We denote by \mathcal{Q} the set of palindromic maximal continuants and by $\hat{\mathcal{Q}}$ the set of non-palindromic maximal continuants $\hat{Q} = (aW)$ such that W is left-balanced (it will become clear that if a non-palindromic maximal continuant is not in this set then its reversal surely is). By \mathcal{W} we denote the set of left-balanced words W which are obtained from continuants $\hat{Q} \in \hat{\mathcal{Q}}$ by skipping the a on the left end, and we write $\mathcal{W}b$ for the set of words (Wb) which are obtained from $W \in \mathcal{W}$ by adding a b on the right end. Similarly, we may write $\hat{\mathcal{Q}} = a\mathcal{W}$. Using an analogous notation and letting \mathcal{F} denote the set of Fine-Wilf words with two coprime periods, we have the identity $\mathcal{Q} = a\mathcal{F}a$ (see [9]). Any $F \in \mathcal{F}$ with periods π, κ ($\pi < \kappa$) can be uniquely written as

$$F = (UVU) = (\Pi^h U)$$

where the subword $(UV) = (\Pi^h)$, $h \geq 1$, is purely periodic and one has $0 \leq |U| < |\Pi| = \pi$. We call this the *standard partition* of F . Since each F is palindromic, one has necessarily $V = V^*$. We denote by \mathcal{F}_a , resp. \mathcal{F}_b , the set of Fine-Wilf words for which the subword Π ends with the letter a , resp. b . Clearly each $F \in \mathcal{F}_a$ is made a word from \mathcal{F}_b by interchanging a 's and b 's, and vice versa.

Theorem 2.

- (i) Let $F(u, w)$ denote the Fine-Wilf word made up of $u - 1$ a 's and $w - 1$ b 's (u, w coprime, $u \geq 2$). Then $F(u, w) \in \mathcal{F}_b$ if and only if the semiregular expansion $\frac{u}{w} = \langle\langle c_1, \dots, c_r; c \rangle\rangle$ ($r \geq 1$) ends with $c = +v$ (≥ 1).
- (ii) There is a one-to-one correspondence between $\hat{\mathcal{Q}}$ and \mathcal{F}_b , given as follows: Let $F = F(u, w)$ be any word from \mathcal{F}_b with standard partition $F = (\Pi^h U)$ and associated semiregular expansion $\frac{u}{w} = \langle\langle c_1, \dots, c_r; v \rangle\rangle$ ($r \geq 1$). Then $\hat{Q} = (aW) \in \hat{\mathcal{Q}}$ where $(Wb) = (\Pi^d)$, with $d = h$ if $|U| = \pi - 1$ or $c_r > 0$, and $d = h - 1$ if $0 \leq |U| \leq \pi - 2$ and $c_r < 0$. Conversely, each $\hat{Q} \in \hat{\mathcal{Q}}$ is obtained in this way from precisely one $F \in \mathcal{F}_b$.
- (iii) Let $(1 \leq) \pi < \kappa$ be the (coprime) periods of F . Then the following implications hold: $\kappa = 1 \pmod{\pi} \Leftrightarrow |U| = \pi - 1$, and $\kappa = k \pmod{\pi}$ ($k = 2, \dots, \pi - 1$) $\Leftrightarrow |U| = k - 2$. Equality $|U| = \pi - 2$ cannot occur.

Remark. Since interchanging the letters a, b in a word F does not affect periodicity, there is no essential difference between the sets \mathcal{F}_a and \mathcal{F}_b , as far as only periodicity properties are involved, and each of the two sets can well represent the whole class \mathcal{F} . The concept of maximality of continuants, however, is based on an (abstract or numerical) order $a < b$, and interchanging letters destroys the maximality of any maximal continuant different from the trivial words $(a^k), (b^k), (ab), (ba)$. This is why $\mathcal{F}_a, \mathcal{F}_b$ lack equivalence in the present context.

3. Proofs

A reduced fraction $\frac{u}{w}$ is called *admissible* if its semiregular expansion $(2')$ ends with $c = +v$ (this is case (2a)). It is readily verified that the admissible fractions have a regular expansion of the form $[a_0; a_1, \dots, a_n]$ with n odd, $a_0 \in \mathbf{N}_0, a_1, \dots, a_n \in \mathbf{N}, a_n \geq 2$; if $a_n = 2$ then only $[0; 2], [0; a, 1^{2j-1}, 2]$ or $[a; b, 1^{2j-1}, 2]$ can occur with $a, b, j \in \mathbf{N}, b \geq 2$. For the last entry a_n there are two obvious possibilities: we have $a_n = v + 2$ if $(2')$ ends with $\langle\langle \dots, -v_r; v \rangle\rangle$, and $a_n = v + 1$ if $(2')$ ends with $\langle\langle \dots, +v_r; v \rangle\rangle$. So either $v = a_n - 2$ or $v = a_n - 1$. But actually neither v nor the sign of c_r , which both play a key role in Theorem 2, can be extracted at low costs from the regular expansion; in general, this requires the whole algorithmic translation of the sequence $(a_0; a_1, \dots, a_n)$ into $(\varepsilon_1 v_1, \dots, \varepsilon_r v_r; c)$.

Given any pair of integers $\ell \geq 1, m \geq 0, (\ell, m) \neq (1, 0)$, it is possible to construct the maximal continuant $Q_{\ell, m}$ made up of ℓ a 's and m b 's by an iterative procedure which we describe briefly (for a more detailed exposition see [9]). It is convenient to introduce the quantities $u = \ell - 1$ and $w = m + 1$. The process starts with three types of lattice points (u_o, w_o) which we call *root points* (or *roots*, for short) and associated balanced words $W_o = W_o(u_o, w_o)$ of length $\lambda_o = \ell_o + m_o = u_o + w_o$ called *root words*:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Ia: } & u_o = 1, w_o \geq 2 \quad \dots \quad W_o = (ab^{w_o-1}a), & \text{II: } & u_o = 0, w_o \geq 2 \quad \dots \quad W_o = (ab^{w_o-1}). \\ \text{Ib: } & u_o \geq 1, w_o = 1 \quad \dots \quad W_o = (a^{u_o+1}), & & \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

Note that the type I root words are palindromic and associated with primitive lattice points, and the type II root words are non-palindromic and associated with non-primitive lattice points. The trivial word (a) corresponding to $u_o = 0, w_o = 1$ is excluded, as there is no systematic need for its occurrence. We now construct inductively a collection \mathcal{B} of balanced words which will be in a one-to-one correspondence with the set $\Lambda = (\mathbf{N}_0 \times \mathbf{N}) \setminus \{(0, 1)\}$ of integer lattice points. Let $W = W(u, w) = (w_1, \dots, w_h)$ ($w_j \in \{a, b\}$) be a word of length $\lambda = u + w$ containing $u + 1$ a 's and $w - 1$ b 's which has already been constructed. Given an arbitrary positive integer v , two new words are constructed by carrying out the formal substitutions

$$\mathcal{H}_{+1}^{\{v\}} : a \mapsto ab^v, b \mapsto ab^{v+1} \quad \text{and} \quad \mathcal{H}_{-1}^{\{v\}} : a \mapsto a^{v+1}b, b \mapsto a^v b.$$

This produces two words $\widetilde{W}_{+1}^{\{v\}}$ and $\widetilde{W}_{-1}^{\{v\}}$. Extend the first word by adding an a on the right end, and shorten the second word by skipping the b on the right end.

In the first case the new word is of the form $W_{+1}^{\{v\}}(u', w') = (ab^{k_1}ab^{k_2} \dots b^{k_\ell}a)$ where $k_j = v$ if $w_j = a$ and $k_j = v + 1$ if $w_j = b$. We call this the *upper right neighbor* of W . Its length is $\lambda' = u' + w' = (v + 1)\lambda + w$, it is made up of $u' + 1$ isolated a 's and $w' - 1$ b 's, and one has

$$\begin{pmatrix} u' \\ w' \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ v & v+1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} u \\ w \end{pmatrix} = S^v T \begin{pmatrix} u \\ w \end{pmatrix} =: H_{+1}^{\{v\}} \begin{pmatrix} u \\ w \end{pmatrix}.$$

In the second case the new word is of the form $W_{-1}^{\{v\}}(u', w') = (a^{i_1}ba^{i_2}b \dots ba^{i_\ell})$ where $i_j = v + 1$ if $w_j = a$ and $i_j = v$ if $w_j = b$. We call this the *upper left neighbor* of W . Its length is $\lambda' = u' + w' = (v + 1)\lambda + u$, it is made up of $u' + 1$ a 's and $w' - 1$ isolated b 's, and one has

$$\begin{pmatrix} u' \\ w' \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} v+1 & v \\ 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} u \\ w \end{pmatrix} = T^v S \begin{pmatrix} u \\ w \end{pmatrix} =: H_{-1}^{\{v\}} \begin{pmatrix} u \\ w \end{pmatrix}.$$

In each step of the construction the balancedness and the symmetry or asymmetry of a word W are inherited by both upper neighbors, and the length of a word is more than doubled. It follows from the unimodularity of the integer matrices S and T that the greatest common divisor $d = \gcd(u, w)$ of the lattice point (u, w) associated with a word W remains unchanged in each step. In particular, the primitivity, resp. non-primitivity, of any (u, w) is hereditary. It is important to note that the transformations (4) are invertible, and each $(u, w) \in \Lambda$ is uniquely attained for some word $W \in \mathcal{B}$. Given any $(u', w') \in \Lambda$, one can trace back the steps of the procedure down to the individual root by the following inverse algorithm:

$$\text{If } 1 < u' < w' \text{ then } (u, w) := ((v+1)u' - w', -vu' + w') \text{ where } v = \lfloor (w' - 1)/u' \rfloor; \tag{5a}$$

$$\text{If } 1 < w' \leq u' \text{ then } (u, w) := (u' - vw', -u' + (v+1)w') \text{ where } v = \lfloor u'/w' \rfloor. \tag{5b}$$

Iterate this until one of the coordinates is 0 or 1. The final pairs are of the form

$$(1, w_o), w_o \geq 2, \text{ or } (u_o, 1), u_o \geq 1 \text{ (then } u', w' \text{ are coprime), or of the form}$$

$$(0, w_o), w_o \geq 2 \text{ (then } w_o = \gcd(u', w')).$$

Remark. Each palindromic (type I) root is of the form $(a\Phi_o a)$ where Φ_o is a (trivial) bi-balanced word. A straightforward induction shows that this property is hereditary in any upward step of the above process: Assume that $(a\Phi a)$ is a word already constructed and the subword Φ is bi-balanced. Then any of the transformations $H_\varepsilon^{\{v\}}$ produces a new word $(a\Phi' a)$ such that Φ' is again bi-balanced. But it is known that the Fine-Wilf words are characterized by being precisely the bi-balanced words (see e.g. [14]), hence each palindromic continuant Q is of the form (aFa) where F is some Fine-Wilf word. Since for any given coprime pair (u, w) the construction yields a unique $Q(u, w)$ made up of $u + 1$ a 's and $w - 1$ b 's, the Fine-Wilf words $F(u, w)$ arising in this way are made up of $u - 1$ a 's and $w - 1$ b 's and therefore run through the whole set \mathcal{F} . This reproves the identity $\mathcal{Q} = (a\mathcal{F}a)$.

The construction sets up a bijection $\Lambda \Leftrightarrow \mathcal{B}$ which can be fully described by the expansion (2'):

The palindromic case. Let $\begin{pmatrix} u \\ w \end{pmatrix}$ ($\gcd(u, w) = 1$) be a primitive point from Λ and let $[a_0; a_1, \dots, a_n] = \langle\langle \varepsilon_1 v_1, \dots, \varepsilon_r v_r; c \rangle\rangle$ be the two expansions of $\frac{u}{w}$. Then the entries of the matrix

$$Y = \begin{pmatrix} x & y \\ s & t \end{pmatrix} = XG, \text{ with } X = \left(S_{\varepsilon_1}^{v_1} S_{-\varepsilon_1} \right) \left(S_{\varepsilon_2}^{v_2} S_{-\varepsilon_2} \right) \cdots \left(S_{\varepsilon_r}^{v_r} S_{-\varepsilon_r} \right),$$

as given by (2) in terms of the data of the semiregular expansion can be expressed in terms of the regular one. The following implications are readily confirmed by use of the translation (1):

$$\begin{aligned} n = 2j + 1 &\Leftrightarrow \frac{x}{s} = [a_0; a_1, \dots, a_{n-1}, a_n - 1], \frac{y}{t} = [a_0; a_1, \dots, a_{n-1}], \\ n = 2j &\Leftrightarrow \frac{y}{t} = [a_0; a_1, \dots, a_{n-1}, a_n - 1], \frac{x}{s} = [a_0; a_1, \dots, a_{n-1}] \end{aligned}$$

($j \in \mathbf{N}_0$). As we have seen, the primitive points (u, w) (which are associated with the palindromic maximal continuants) are precisely the descendents of the type I roots. We have to distinguish three subcases.

- The root is a type Ib point $(u_o, w_o) = (v + 1, 1)$ ($v \geq 1$), associated with the root word $W(v + 1, 1) = (a^{v+2})$ ($v \geq 1$). Then the expansion (2') of $\frac{u}{w}$ ends with $c = -v$ and we have $\begin{pmatrix} u \\ w \end{pmatrix} = XT^v \mathbf{e}$. We denote by Λ_- the set of lattice points of this kind and by \mathcal{Q}_- the set of associated continuants.

- The root is the type Ib point $(u_o, w_o) = (1, 1)$, associated with the root word $W(1, 1) = (aa)$. Then the expansion (2') of $\frac{u}{w}$ ends with $c = 0$ and we have $\begin{pmatrix} u \\ w \end{pmatrix} = X\mathbf{e}$. We denote by Λ_0 the set of lattice points of this kind and by \mathcal{Q}_0 the set of associated continuants.

- The root is a type Ia point $(u_o, w_o) = (1, v + 1)$ ($v \geq 1$), associated with the root word $W(1, v + 1) = (ab^v a)$. Then the expansion (2') of $\frac{u}{w}$ ends with $c = +v$ ($v \geq 1$) and we have $\begin{pmatrix} u \\ w \end{pmatrix} = XS^v \mathbf{e}$, in other words, the descendents of type Ia roots are precisely those for which $\frac{u}{w}$ is admissible. We denote by Λ_+ the set of lattice points $\begin{pmatrix} \tilde{u} \\ \tilde{w} \end{pmatrix} = XS^v \mathbf{e}$ ($v \geq 1$) and by \mathcal{Q}_+ the set of associated continuants. It makes sense to call all these points and also the associated continuants $\tilde{Q} \in \mathcal{Q}_+$ *admissible*.

The non-palindromic case. We denote by $\hat{\Lambda}$ the set of non-primitive points $\begin{pmatrix} \hat{u} \\ \hat{w} \end{pmatrix}$ from Λ . They are the descendents of the type II roots $(u_o, w_o) = (0, d)$, $d \geq 2$, with associated root words $W_o = (ab^{d-1})$. The words derived from these root words are precisely the non-palindromic maximal continuants \hat{Q} (remember that we identify each \hat{Q} with its reversal \hat{Q}^*). Any point derived from a root $(0, d)$ is of the form $\begin{pmatrix} \hat{u} \\ \hat{w} \end{pmatrix} = d \begin{pmatrix} y \\ t \end{pmatrix}$, with $\begin{pmatrix} y \\ t \end{pmatrix}$ in lowest terms. Obviously, there is a bijection $\hat{Q} \leftrightarrow \mathcal{Q}_+$ (and thus $\hat{Q} \leftrightarrow \mathcal{F}_+ \leftrightarrow \Lambda_+$) based on the one-to-one correspondence between

the non-primitive points $\begin{pmatrix} \hat{u} \\ \hat{w} \end{pmatrix} = X \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ d \end{pmatrix}$, $d \geq 2$, (having root words (ab^{d-1})), and

the admissible primitive points $\begin{pmatrix} \tilde{u} \\ \tilde{w} \end{pmatrix} = XS^{d-1} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} = X \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ d \end{pmatrix}$ (having root words $(ab^{d-1}a)$).

We will verify all assertions of our theorems by comparing the structure of the continuants \hat{Q} associated with the points $\begin{pmatrix} \hat{u} \\ \hat{w} \end{pmatrix}$ with that of the continuants \tilde{Q} associated with the points $\begin{pmatrix} \tilde{u} \\ \tilde{w} \end{pmatrix}$.

We need two dualities on Λ which are mirrored by the regular and semiregular expansions of reduced fractions. First we study the effect of interchanging the coordinates of a point to the associated continuant. We have just seen that the set $\bar{\Lambda}$ of primitive points from Λ is the disjoint union $\Lambda_- \cup \Lambda_0 \cup \Lambda_+$. If u, w are coprime and $\frac{u}{w} = \langle\langle c_1, \dots, c_r; c \rangle\rangle = [a_0; a_1, \dots, a_n]$ then clearly $\{(1 \leq) u < w \Leftrightarrow c_1 = +v_1 (\geq 1) \Leftrightarrow a_0 = 0\}$ and $\{u > w \Leftrightarrow c_1 = -v_1 (\leq -1) \Leftrightarrow a_0 \geq 1\}$. Let $P = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$. Since $P \begin{pmatrix} u \\ w \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} w \\ u \end{pmatrix}$ and $PS_\varepsilon P = S_{-\varepsilon}$, one gets the coordinates interchanged by interchanging the matrices S, T in the factorization (1), which results in interchanging the signs in the expansion (2')

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{u}{w} &= [a_0; a_1, \dots, a_n] = \langle\langle +v_1, c_2, \dots, c_r; c \rangle\rangle \quad (> 1) \\ \Leftrightarrow \frac{w}{u} &= [0; a_0, a_1, \dots, a_n] = \langle\langle -v_1, -c_2, \dots, -c_r; -c \rangle\rangle \quad (< 1). \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

From (7) we infer the identities $P\Lambda_- = \Lambda_+$, $P\Lambda_+ = \Lambda_-$ and $P\Lambda_0 = \Lambda_0$. This duality induced by the reflection P defined on $\bar{\Lambda}$ carries over to $\bar{\mathcal{Q}} = \mathcal{Q}_- \cup \mathcal{Q}_0 \cup \mathcal{Q}_+$ as well as to \mathcal{F} and also to the class \mathcal{Y} of integer matrices Y with non-negative entries and $\det(Y) = 1$. If $Q \in \bar{\mathcal{Q}}$ is associated with (u, w) , we write Q^\dagger for the maximal palindromic continuant associated with (w, u) . In particular, we have $W_{(1, v+1)}^\dagger = (ab^v a)^\dagger = W_{(v+1, 1)} = (a^{v+2})$ for the root words associated with the type Ia roots $(1, v+1)$ and the type Ib roots $(v+1, 1)$ ($v \geq 1$). The root word $W_{(1, 1)} = (aa)$ is the only word in $\bar{\mathcal{Q}}$ which is mapped to itself. Clearly $\mathcal{Q}_-^\dagger = \mathcal{Q}_+$, $\mathcal{Q}_+^\dagger = \mathcal{Q}_-$ and $\mathcal{Q}_0^\dagger = \mathcal{Q}_0$. Given any $F \in \mathcal{F}$, we write F^\dagger for the word obtained by interchanging the a 's and b 's. Clearly F^\dagger is again a Fine-Wilf word. We need a refinement of the identities $\bar{\mathcal{Q}} = a\mathcal{F}a$ and $\mathcal{F}^\dagger = \mathcal{F}$ which follows by a simple modification of the arguments in the proof of Th.3 (iii) in [9]:

$$Q = (aFa) \in \mathcal{Q}_\varepsilon \Leftrightarrow Q^\dagger = (aF^\dagger a) \in \mathcal{Q}_{-\varepsilon} \quad (\varepsilon \in \{-1, 0, +1\}).$$

(Here and later the suffix $+1$ or -1 of course has the same meaning as $+$ or $-$). Motivated by (8a) we denote by \mathcal{F}_ε ($\varepsilon \in \{-1, 0, +1\}$) the set of Fine-Wilf words such that $(aFa) \in \mathcal{Q}_\varepsilon$. Clearly $\mathcal{F} = \mathcal{F}_- \cup \mathcal{F}_0 \cup \mathcal{F}_+$ and $\mathcal{F}_\varepsilon^\dagger = \mathcal{F}_{-\varepsilon}$. As we will see later (cf. (11)), one has $\mathcal{F}_b = \mathcal{F}_+$ and $\mathcal{F}_a = \mathcal{F}_- \cup \mathcal{F}_0$. Analogously, we obtain a partition of \mathcal{Y} by defining \mathcal{Y}_ε ($\varepsilon \in \{-1, 0, +1\}$) to be the set of matrices $Y \in \mathcal{Y}$ such that $Ye \in \mathcal{Q}_\varepsilon$. As we have seen, there is a bijection $\mathcal{Y} \leftrightarrow \bar{\Lambda}$ induced by the equality $Ye = \begin{pmatrix} u \\ w \end{pmatrix} \in \bar{\Lambda}$. Given any $Y \in \mathcal{Y} = \begin{pmatrix} x & y \\ s & t \end{pmatrix}$, we write $Y^\dagger = PYP = \begin{pmatrix} t & s \\ y & x \end{pmatrix}$. From the relations $S = PTP$, $T = PSP$ it follows at once that

$$Y \in \mathcal{Y}_\varepsilon \Leftrightarrow Y^\dagger \in \mathcal{Y}_{-\varepsilon} \quad \text{and} \quad Ye \in \Lambda_\varepsilon \Leftrightarrow Y^\dagger e \in \Lambda_{-\varepsilon} \quad (\varepsilon \in \{-1, 0, +1\}).$$

We can now collect the desired details of the bijection $\hat{\mathcal{Q}} \leftrightarrow \mathcal{Q}_+$. Given any palindromic $\tilde{Q} \in \mathcal{Q}_+$, let $\begin{pmatrix} \tilde{u} \\ \tilde{w} \end{pmatrix} = Ye = \begin{pmatrix} x & y \\ s & t \end{pmatrix} e = XS^{d-1}e = X \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ d \end{pmatrix}$ ($d \geq 2$) be the associated (admissible) point from Λ_+ . Then $Y \in \mathcal{Y}_+$, and one has $\frac{\tilde{u}}{\tilde{w}} = \langle\langle c_1, \dots, c_r; d-1 \rangle\rangle = [a_0; a_1, \dots, a_n]$, n odd. Remember that

$$d = \begin{cases} a_n & \text{if } c_r > 0, \\ a_n - 1 & \text{if } c_r < 0. \end{cases} \tag{9a, b}$$

Since $X = \begin{pmatrix} x-(d-1)y & y \\ s-(d-1)t & t \end{pmatrix}$, the corresponding non-palindromic $\hat{Q} \in \hat{\mathcal{Q}}$ is associated with the point $\begin{pmatrix} \hat{u} \\ \hat{w} \end{pmatrix} = X \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ d \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} yd \\ td \end{pmatrix}$. Conversely, given any triple $(y, t; d)$ (y, t coprime, $d \geq 2$), it is easy to construct the primitive point $\begin{pmatrix} \tilde{u} \\ \tilde{w} \end{pmatrix} \in \Lambda_+$ corresponding to the non-primitive point $\begin{pmatrix} yd \\ td \end{pmatrix}$.

The following diagram exhibits the structural relationships.

$$\begin{array}{ccccccc}
 \hat{Q} = (aW) \in \hat{\mathcal{Q}} \dots (Wb) = (\Pi^d) & \leftrightarrow & \begin{pmatrix} \hat{u} \\ \hat{w} \end{pmatrix} = d \begin{pmatrix} y \\ t \end{pmatrix} \dots \frac{y}{t} = [\dots, a_{n-1}] \\
 \downarrow & & & & & & \\
 \tilde{W}_o = (ab^v a) \rightarrow \tilde{Q} = (a\tilde{F}a) = (a\Pi^h Ua) \in \mathcal{Q}_+ \leftrightarrow \tilde{F} \in \mathcal{F}_+ \leftrightarrow \begin{pmatrix} \tilde{u} \\ \tilde{w} \end{pmatrix} \in \Lambda_+ \leftrightarrow \frac{\tilde{u}}{\tilde{w}} = \langle\langle c_1, \dots; (d-1) \rangle\rangle \\
 & & & & & & = [\dots, a_{n-1}, a_n] \\
 \downarrow & & \downarrow & & \downarrow & & \downarrow \\
 \tilde{W}_o^\uparrow = (a^{v+2}) \rightarrow \tilde{Q}^\uparrow = (a\tilde{F}^\uparrow a) \in \mathcal{Q}_- & \leftrightarrow & \tilde{F}^\uparrow \in \mathcal{F}_- \leftrightarrow \begin{pmatrix} \tilde{w} \\ \tilde{u} \end{pmatrix} \in \Lambda_- \leftrightarrow \frac{\tilde{w}}{\tilde{u}} = \langle\langle -c_1, \dots; -(d-1) \rangle\rangle \\
 W_o = (a^2) \rightarrow Q = (aFa) \in \mathcal{Q}_0 & \leftrightarrow & F \in \mathcal{F}_0 \leftrightarrow \begin{pmatrix} u \\ w \end{pmatrix} \in \Lambda_0 \leftrightarrow \frac{u}{w} = \langle\langle c_1, \dots, c_r; 0 \rangle\rangle \\
 \downarrow & & \downarrow & & \downarrow & & \downarrow \\
 W_o^\uparrow = (a^2) \rightarrow Q^\uparrow = (aF^\uparrow a) \in \mathcal{Q}_0 & \leftrightarrow & F^\uparrow \in \mathcal{F}_0 \leftrightarrow \begin{pmatrix} w \\ u \end{pmatrix} \in \Lambda_0 \leftrightarrow \frac{w}{u} = \langle\langle -c_1, \dots, -c_r; 0 \rangle\rangle
 \end{array}$$

There is a second duality on $\bar{\Lambda}$, induced by transposition on \mathcal{Y} . Given any $\mathbf{u} = \begin{pmatrix} u \\ w \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} x+y \\ s+t \end{pmatrix} = Y\mathbf{e} \in \bar{\Lambda}$ with associated matrix $Y = \begin{pmatrix} x & y \\ s & t \end{pmatrix} \in \mathcal{Y}$, we write $\mathbf{u}^\Delta = Y^{\text{tr}}\mathbf{e} = \begin{pmatrix} x+s \\ y+t \end{pmatrix}$. Clearly $\mathbf{u}^{\Delta\Delta} = \mathbf{u}$. Since $\mathcal{Y}^{\text{tr}} = \mathcal{Y}$, one has $\bar{\Lambda}^\Delta = \bar{\Lambda}$. Let F be the Fine-Wilf word with two coprime periods κ and π , made up of $u-1$ a 's and $w-1$ b 's. It is known (see e.g. [14], [15] or [9]) that one has $\begin{pmatrix} \kappa \\ \pi \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} u \\ w \end{pmatrix}^\Delta$. It follows from (1) that this duality can be expressed by means of regular continued fractions. Let $u/w = [a_0; a_1, \dots, a_n]$, $a_0 \in \mathbf{N}_0$, $a_1, \dots, a_n \in \mathbf{N}$, $a_n \geq 2$;

$$\begin{array}{l}
 \text{if } n = 2j, \quad j \geq 1, a_0 \geq 1, \text{ then } \kappa/\pi = [0; a_n-1, a_{n-1}, \dots, a_1, a_0+1] (< 1), \\
 \text{if } n = 2j, \quad j \geq 1, a_0 = 0, \text{ then } \kappa/\pi = [0; a_n-1, a_{n-1}, \dots, a_2, a_1+1] (< 1); \\
 \text{if } n = 2j+1, j \geq 0, a_0 \geq 1, \text{ then } \kappa/\pi = [a_n-1; a_{n-1}, \dots, a_1, a_0+1] (> 1), \\
 \text{if } n = 2j+1, j \geq 1, a_0 = 0, \text{ then } \kappa/\pi = [a_n-1; a_{n-1}, \dots, a_2, a_1+1] (> 1).
 \end{array} \tag{10a, b, c, d}$$

For the type I root points (which are not covered by the above table) we have $\begin{pmatrix} u \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}^\Delta = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ u \end{pmatrix}$ ($u \geq 2$). Note that a point $\mathbf{u} = Y\mathbf{e}$ is selfdual iff Y is symmetric. For completeness, we admit the trivial point \mathbf{e} associated with $\frac{1}{1} = [1;] = [0; 1]$ which may also run as selfdual. If, in particular, $\begin{pmatrix} u \\ w \end{pmatrix} \in \Lambda_+$ ($\Leftrightarrow Q = (aFa) \in \mathcal{Q}_+ \Leftrightarrow F \in \mathcal{F}_+$), then n is odd, which implies that π is the smaller one of the two periods. Note the equalities $|F| + 2 = |Q| = u + w = \kappa + \pi$.

Let F be a word from \mathcal{F}_+ associated with the point $\frac{u}{w} = Y\mathbf{e}$, $Y = \begin{pmatrix} x & y \\ s & t \end{pmatrix}$. Then $\pi = y + t$. It is known (see [14]) that the places of the b 's in a word $F \in \mathcal{F}_+$ are given by the numbers $\lfloor (1 + \frac{y}{t})k \rfloor (= \lfloor \frac{k\pi}{t} \rfloor)$, $k = 1, \dots, w - 1 (= s + t - 1)$. Letting $k = t, 2t, \dots$, we conclude that the letters on the places $\pi, 2\pi, \dots$ are b 's. This implies the announced identity

$$\mathcal{F}_b = \mathcal{F}_+ \tag{11}$$

Given any $F \in \mathcal{F}_b = \mathcal{F}_+$ with standard partition $F = (\Pi^h U)$, one has $|F| = \kappa + \pi - 2 = h\pi + |U|$, $|U| \in \{0, \dots, \pi - 1\}$, hence $h - 1 = \lfloor \frac{\kappa - 2}{\pi} \rfloor$. On the other hand, we infer from the relations (10c,d) that $\kappa = (a_n - 1)\pi + k$, with $k \in \{1, \dots, \pi - 1\}$ and $a_n - 1 = \lfloor \frac{\kappa}{\pi} \rfloor$. We distinguish two cases.

- $\kappa = 1 \pmod{\pi}$. Then necessarily $n = 1$, $\kappa = (a_1 - 1)\pi + 1$, $\frac{\kappa}{\pi} = [a_1 - 1; \pi]$, $\frac{\tilde{u}}{\tilde{w}} = [\pi - 1; a_1] = \langle\langle -(\pi - 1); a_1 - 2 \rangle\rangle$, $a_1 \geq 3$. Since here $c_r = c_1 < 0$, it follows from (9b) that $d = a_1 - 1$. The equality $\kappa + \pi - 2 = a_1\pi - 1 = (a_1 - 1)\pi + (\pi - 1)$ shows that $h = a_1 - 1$. In summary, we have $d = h$ and $|U| = \pi - 1$. The associated palindromic continuant \tilde{Q} is the upper neighbor of the root word $(ab^{d-1}a)$ obtained by applying the transformation $T^{\pi-1}S = H_{-1}^{\{\pi-1\}}$ (see (4b)) which gives $\tilde{Q} = (aFa) = (a\Pi^d Ua)$, with $\Pi = (a^{\pi-1}b)$, $U = (a^{\pi-1})$. Starting from the root word $(ab^{d-1}a)$ and applying the same transformation, one gets the corresponding non-palindromic continuant $\hat{Q} = (aW)$, where $(Wb) = (\Pi^d)$. (Wb) has no second period in the present case, since $|(Wb)| = \pi d < \pi d + 1 = \kappa$.
- $\kappa = k \pmod{\pi}$, $k \in \{2, \dots, \pi - 1\}$. Then $\kappa = (a_n - 1)\pi + k$. Since here $\kappa + \pi - 2 = a_n\pi + k - 2$, we have $h = a_n$ and $k - 2 = |U| \in \{0, \dots, \pi - 3\}$. If the entry c_r in the semiregular expansion of the associated fraction $\frac{\tilde{u}}{\tilde{w}}$ is positive then we have $d = a_n = h$, by (9a), and $(Wb) = (\Pi^d)$ has κ as a second period, since $|(Wb)| = \pi d = \pi(d - 1) + \pi > \pi(d - 1) + k = \kappa$; otherwise we have $d = a_n - 1 = h - 1 (\geq 2)$, by (9b), and (Wb) has no second period, since now $|(Wb)| = \pi d < \pi d + k = \kappa$.

The assertions of our theorems now follow on combining the above results with relations (9) and the fact that each $\hat{Q}(\hat{u}, \hat{w}) \in \hat{\mathcal{Q}}$ begins with an a and has length $|\hat{Q}| = \hat{u} + \hat{w} = (y + t)d = \pi d = |\Pi^d| = |(Wb)|$. The subword W is left-balanced because both W and (Wb) are leftmost subwords of a bi-balanced (and so, a fortiori, left-balanced) word, but W is not right-balanced because (bWa) fails to be balanced, no matter whether W has isolated a 's or isolated b 's. The proofs of Theorems 1 and 2 are complete.

4. Examples

a. Let F be the Fine-Wilf word with periods $(\kappa, \pi) = (24, 7)$. Then $\frac{\kappa}{\pi} = [3; 2, 3]$, hence the associated primitive fraction is $\frac{\tilde{u}}{\tilde{w}} = [0; 2, 2, 4] = [a_0; \dots, a_3]$ (note that we have to take care that n is odd; the alternative choice $[2; 2, 4]$ here would violate this necessary condition for a fraction to be admissible). It follows that $\left(\frac{\tilde{u}}{\tilde{w}}\right) = T^{a_0} S^{a_1} T^{a_2} S^{a_3-1} \mathbf{e} = S^2 T^2 S^3 \mathbf{e} = Y \mathbf{e} = \begin{pmatrix} 7 & 2 \\ 17 & 5 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 9 \\ 22 \end{pmatrix}$. Resetting brackets gives the representation $Y = (S^2 T)(TS)S^2$, hence the semiregular expansion reads $\frac{\tilde{u}}{\tilde{w}} = \langle\langle 2, -1; 2 \rangle\rangle = \langle\langle c_1, c_2; d - 1 \rangle\rangle$ which shows that $\frac{\tilde{u}}{\tilde{w}}$ is admissible and so $F \in \mathcal{F}_+ (= \mathcal{F}_b)$. The word \tilde{Q} made up of $\tilde{u} + 1 = 10$ a 's and $\tilde{w} - 1 = 21$ b 's is constructed in two steps from the root word $W_o = (ab^{d-1}a) = (abba)$. First we apply the transformation $H_{-1}^{\{v_2\}} = T^{v_2} S = TS$ (see (4b)) to obtain the word $(aabababaa)$, then we apply $H_{+1}^{\{v_1\}} = S^{v_1} T = S^2 T$ (see (4a)) to end up with $\tilde{Q} = (a\|bbabbab\|bbabbab\|bbabbab\|bbabbab\|b\|a) = (aFa)$, where $F = (\Pi^h U)$, with $h = \lfloor \frac{\kappa - 2}{\pi} \rfloor + 1 = 4$, $\Pi = (bbabbab)$, $|\Pi| = \pi = 7$, and $U = (b)$, $|U| = \kappa + \pi - 2 - h\pi = 1$.

Since $Y = XS^{d-1} = X \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 2 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$, we have $X = \begin{pmatrix} 3 & 2 \\ 7 & 5 \end{pmatrix}$. Therefore the corresponding non-palindromic \hat{Q} is associated with the non-primitive point $\begin{pmatrix} \hat{u} \\ \hat{w} \end{pmatrix} = X \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ d \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} yd \\ td \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 6 \\ 15 \end{pmatrix}$. We have $d=3=a_3-1$, in accordance with the rule (9b). We construct \hat{Q} by starting from the type I root word $(ab^{d-1}) = (abb)$ and applying the same transformations as above. The first step gives $(aababa)$, the second one $\hat{Q} = (a\|bbabbab\|bbabbab\|bbabba)$. According to our theorems, we have $\hat{Q} = (aW)$, with $(Wb) = (\Pi^d) = (\Pi^3)$. The word $W = (bbabbab\|bbabbab\|bbabba)$ is left-balanced but not right-balanced, as (aWb) is still balanced, but (bWa) obviously fails to be balanced since it has a double a on the right end, whereas the a 's in W are isolated.

b. We consider the immediate neighbors of the root words appearing in the previous example. Let $(\kappa, \pi) = (7, 2)$. Here $\kappa = 1 \pmod{\pi}$, $\frac{\kappa}{\pi} = [a_1 - 1; \pi] = [3; 2]$, $\frac{\tilde{u}}{w} = [\pi - 1; a_1] = [1; 4] = \langle\langle -(\pi - 1); a_1 - 2 \rangle\rangle = \langle\langle -1; 2 \rangle\rangle$, hence $d = h = a_1 - 1 = 3$ (like in example 1 and in any conceivable later step), and $|U| = \pi - 1 = 1$. Starting from the root word $(ab^{d-1}a) = (abba)$, we apply $TS = H_{-1}^{\{1\}}$ to obtain $\tilde{Q} = (a\|ab\|ab\|ab\|a) = (aFa)$, with $F = (\Pi^h U)$, $\Pi = (ab)$, $|\Pi| = \pi = 2$, $U = (a)$, $|U| = \kappa + \pi - 2 - h\pi = 1$. On the other hand, starting from the type I root word $(ab^{d-1}) = (abb)$ and again applying $H_{-1}^{\{1\}}$, we are led to $\hat{Q} = (a\|ab\|ab\|a) = (aW)$, with $(Wb) = (\Pi^d) = (\Pi^3)$.

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